

MODELING OF FORMING OF FABRIC-REINFORCED THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITES

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Summary: TWINTEX® composites are fabric-reinforced thermoplastic composites (FRTPC) made with commingled yarns of PP/glass fibers. The mechanical behavior of the material in large deformation and at processing temperature are far from being well understood. The objective of the research is to determine a constitutive law used for modeling the FRTPC in forming process. A series of bias-extension tests are performed to study the stress-strain behavior of the material. Based on the experimental results, a non-isothermal orthotropic hyperelastic model is employed for modeling these materials. The finite element formulation based on the membrane theory is developed for describing the deformation of FRTPC during forming process.

Key terms: characterization, modeling, thermoplastic composites, forming, finite element method.

INTRODUCTION

TWINTEX® is a commingled roving made of glass and polypropylene fibers. The unique commingled structure of TWINTEX® makes it easy for the polypropylene fibers to wet out the glass fibers in a variety of processes, making continuous fiber composites. These vary from low-pressure processes such as vacuum molding, filament winding, and pultrusion, to high-pressure processes like stamping, co-molding, extrusion compression, or injection molding. TWINTEX® is easily converted into FRTPC by heating the material above the melting point of PP (165° C) from 392° F (200° C) to 428° F (220° C). During heating, the polypropylene flows under pressure to form the matrix of the composites.

There is considerable application of FRTPC materials for aerospace and automotive components. These materials have advantages over traditional thermosetting preregs in that components may be thermoformed with short cycle times by hot stamping, roll forming or diaphragm forming. Thermoplastic composites could also have good mechanical properties and be easily recycled. The practical difficulties of forming successful thermoformed components has led to a requirement for understanding the rheological properties of FRTPC sheets and for the development of computational techniques for process simulations based on these properties. While the experimental method may be used to understand the forming of these materials, numerical simulations offer an efficient and rapid tool to study the mechanism of deformation of FRTPC sheets.

The deformation of FRTPC sheets has been studied in some papers [1-5] where the material flow is governed by different laws of fluid mechanics. Some other authors [6-9] have modeled the deformation of anisotropic composites using an approach of solid mechanics. In this paper, the deformation of FRTPC sheets during forming is governed by an orthotropic hyperelastic model of the solid mechanics. The advantage of the solid mechanic approach compared to the fluid one is the use of Lagrangian mesh for describing the deformation of the materials, in which each material element is observed and conserved during deformation and the fiber distribution in the final part can be well determined. This is very important for analyzing and optimizing the structure of the composite part afterward. In this study, FRTPC sheets were characterized by the bias-extension tests performed with a tensile test machine at

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several temperatures. In-plane deformations of the composite sheet under load are investigated. The displacement in the load direction and the evolution of the fibers angle are used to characterize the mechanical behavior of the FRTPC materials. A characterization method was developed in order to determine the direct relationship between the stress and stretch ratio through an orthotropic hyperelastic model. The thermoplastic matrix is considered incompressible. A method of nonlinear curve fitting was used to fit experimental data to the mentioned model in order to determine its parameters. The WLF function was used to depict the temperature dependence. Finally, the finite element formulation was developed for non-linear material and large deformation by using the membrane theory. This model was implemented in Formsim which is a finite element software developed at IMI for the forming of thermoplastic and fiber-reinforced thermoplastic materials.

MODELING

The deformation of FRTPC sheets during forming is considered as one of an anisotropic solid. As the fibers are initially orthogonal, the mechanical behavior of the material is assumed to be governed by an orthotropic hyperelastic model of continuum mechanics which is defined as the relationship between the second Piola-Kirchhoff stress tensor \mathbf{S} and the deformation tensor \mathbf{C} as follows:

$$\mathbf{S} = 2 \frac{\partial W(\mathbf{C}, \mathbf{a}_0, \mathbf{b}_0)}{\partial \mathbf{C}}, \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{C} = \mathbf{F}^T \cdot \mathbf{F}$ and the deformation gradient tensor $\mathbf{F} = \partial \mathbf{x} / \partial \mathbf{X}$. The strain energy W is a function of \mathbf{C} and the fiber direction unit vectors $\mathbf{a}_0, \mathbf{b}_0$ in the reference configuration. Spencer [10] showed that for the incompressible material the following form is valid:

$$W = W(\mathbf{C}, \mathbf{a}_0, \mathbf{b}_0) = W(I_1, I_2, I_4, I_5, I_6, I_7, I_8, I_9) - \frac{1}{2} p(I_3 - 1), \quad (2)$$

where p is the arbitrary pressure and if $2\theta_0$ denotes the angle between two families of fibers in the reference configuration, the nine invariants of \mathbf{C} are defined by

$$\begin{aligned} I_1 &= tr(\mathbf{C}) & I_2 &= \frac{1}{2} \left\{ (tr(\mathbf{C}))^2 - tr(\mathbf{C}^2) \right\} & I_3 &= \det(\mathbf{C}) \\ I_4 &= \mathbf{a}_0 \cdot \mathbf{C} \cdot \mathbf{a}_0 & I_5 &= \mathbf{a}_0 \cdot \mathbf{C}^2 \cdot \mathbf{a}_0 & I_6 &= \mathbf{b}_0 \cdot \mathbf{C} \cdot \mathbf{b}_0 \\ I_7 &= \mathbf{b}_0 \cdot \mathbf{C}^2 \cdot \mathbf{b}_0 & I_8 &= \cos(2\theta_0) \mathbf{a}_0 \cdot \mathbf{C} \cdot \mathbf{b}_0 & I_9 &= (\mathbf{a}_0 \cdot \mathbf{b}_0)^2 = \cos^2(2\theta_0) \end{aligned}$$

As the fibers are initially orthogonal and if we consider only the first order terms of the strain energy function, Eq 2 becomes

$$W = W(\mathbf{C}, \mathbf{a}_0, \mathbf{b}_0) = W(I_1, I_2, I_4, I_6, \mathbf{a}_0, \mathbf{b}_0) - \frac{1}{2} p(I_3 - 1). \quad (3)$$

By substituting Eq (3) in Eq (1) and with some mathematical transformations we get the constitutive law as follows:

$$\mathbf{S} = 2(W_1 + W_2 I_1) \delta - 2W_2 \mathbf{C} - p \mathbf{C}^{-1} + 2W_4 (\mathbf{a}_0 \otimes \mathbf{a}_0) + 2W_6 (\mathbf{b}_0 \otimes \mathbf{b}_0), \quad (4)$$

where the symbol \otimes stands for the tensor product and $W_k = \partial W / \partial I_k$. Explicitly, the following form of the strain energy equation is used for modeling the FRTPC materials

$$W = M_1 (I_1 - 3) + M_2 (I_2 - 3) + M_3 (I_1 - 3)(I_2 - 3) + M_4 (I_4 - 1) + M_6 (I_6 - 1), \quad (5)$$

where M_k are the parameters of the orthotropic model. The thickness of FRTPC sheets is relatively small in comparison to other dimensions. It is therefore reasonable to apply the membrane theory to study the deformation of FRTPC sheets in forming processes. A membrane has a plane stress state. So the stress in the thickness of the membrane vanishes. By using this condition, the membrane formulation of this constitutive law has the index form as follows:

$$S_{MK} = \begin{pmatrix} 2W_1 \delta_{MK} + 2W_2 I_1 \delta_{MK} - 2W_2 C_{MK} + 2W_2 \lambda_3^4 C_{MK}^{-1} \\ -2W_1 \lambda_3^2 C_{MK}^{-1} - 2W_2 I_1 \lambda_3^2 C_{MK}^{-1} + 2W_4 a_{0M} a_{0K} + 2W_6 b_{0M} b_{0K} \end{pmatrix} \quad (6)$$

where λ_3 is the stretch ratio in the thickness direction.

PARAMETER DETERMINATION

Bias-extension tests

Figure 1. Schematics of the bias extension test.

Lebrun et al. [4-5] studied the mechanical behavior of PP/glass fabric materials using bias-extension tests. Figure 1 shows the schematics of the experimental set-up. Table 1 summarizes the testing conditions considered in this work. The test consists of a sample of a single layer of reinforcement installed in the jaws of a tensile testing machine and having the fibers in the warp and weft directions oriented at $\pm 45^\circ$ from the loading direction. The samples were stretched using an Instron testing machine in a temperature conditioning chamber. By recording the force versus time data and by measuring the angle between the fibers, the force curve versus the stretch ratio in the longitudinal and transverse directions of the sample can be obtained. In this study, a 44 oz/yd² twill 2x2 fabric, commercialized by Vetrotex Certainteed Inc. under the trade name TWINTEX and made with commingled yarns of PP/glass fibers, was employed.

Table 1. Bias extension tests.

Material	TWINTEX 44 oz/yd ² twill 2x2 fabric
Sample dimensions	222.3 mm x 88.9 mm x 1mm
Temperatures	155°C, 170°C and 185°C
Velocity	100 mm/min.

Characterization method

Based on the membrane theory, a characterization method for the bias extension test is developed in order to determine the direct relationship between the Cauchy stress σ_{11} in the load direction and stretch ratios λ_1, λ_2 respectively in the load and transverse directions through the orthotropic hyperelastic model. The characterizing equation corresponding to Eqs (5) and (6) has the following form:

$$\sigma_{11} = 2W_1(\lambda_1^2 - \lambda_2^2) - 2W_2\left(\frac{1}{\lambda_1^2} - \frac{1}{\lambda_2^2}\right) + 2(W_4 + W_6)\{\lambda_1^2 \sin^2(\theta_0) - \lambda_2^2 \cos^2(\theta_0)\}. \quad (7)$$

Curve fitting

The parameters of the model at each temperature are determined by fitting Eq (7) to the experimental data obtained by Lebrun et al. [4-5]. Figure 2 shows the fitting curves and the experimental data of the bias extension tests performed at three temperatures as shown in Table 1.

Figure 2. Fitting curves and experimental data.

Figure 3. Fitting curves of WLF function.

It is reasonable to assume that the temperature dependence of the fiber is negligible in comparison with that of the matrix of the composite. As a consequence, only the three first parameters are temperature dependent and determined by using the WLF function, which defined as follows:

$$aT = \exp\{-C_1 * (T - T_{ref}) / (C_2 + T - T_{ref})\} \quad (8)$$

where C_1 , C_2 are two coefficients to be determined and T_{ref} , T are the reference temperature and the temperature variable. Figure 3 shows the temperature dependence of three parameters M_1 , M_2 and M_3 . Good fits are found with WLF function. The resulting parameters are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Model and WLF function parameters.

M_1	M_2	M_3	T_{ref}	C_1	C_2	M_4	M_6
5.779KPa	7.542KPa	20KPa	155°C	2.427256	16.90609	2.899KPa	2.899KPa

FINITE ELEMENT FORMULATION

The proposed model can be solved numerically by the finite element approximation, in which the formulation is developed based on the virtual work principle and the incremental method.

Virtual work principle in Lagrangian variables

The equation of the virtual work principle described in Lagrangian variables has the following form [11-14]:

$$\int_V \langle \delta \mathbf{E} \rangle \cdot \{\mathbf{S}\} dV = \int_V \rho \langle \delta \mathbf{u} \rangle \cdot \{\mathbf{b}\} dV + \int_A \langle \delta \mathbf{u} \rangle \cdot \{\mathbf{T}\} dA, \quad (9)$$

where \mathbf{E} , \mathbf{u} , \mathbf{b} , ρ and \mathbf{T} are the Green-Lagrange deformation tensor, the displacement vector, the unit volume force, the density and the unit surface force respectively.

Incremental formulation

By applying the increment operator on Eq (9), we get directly the incremental formulation of the studied problem [15-18]

$$\int_V \{ ([{}^T \mathbf{B}_{ll}] + [{}^T \mathbf{B}_{nl}]) [\mathbf{D}] ([\mathbf{B}_{ll}] + [\mathbf{B}_{nl}]) \{ \Delta \mathbf{u}^n \} + [{}^T \mathbf{G}] [\mathbf{\Pi}] [\mathbf{G}] \{ \Delta \mathbf{u}^n \} \} dV = \int_A [{}^T \mathbf{\Psi}] \{ \Delta \mathbf{T} \} dA + \int_V \rho [{}^T \mathbf{\Psi}] \{ \Delta \mathbf{b} \} dV \quad (10)$$

where \mathbf{B}_{ll} , \mathbf{B}_{nl} , $\mathbf{\Psi}$, \mathbf{G} are the transformation matrices, \mathbf{D} the material stiffness matrix, $\mathbf{\Pi}$ the stress stiffness matrix and $\Delta \mathbf{u}^n$ the increment of the nodal displacement vector.

Material stiffness matrix

The stiffness matrix \mathbf{D} is determined by the following equation

$$\frac{1}{2} \mathbf{D} = \frac{\partial \mathbf{S}}{\partial \mathbf{C}} = \begin{pmatrix} 2\delta \otimes \frac{\partial W_1}{\partial \mathbf{C}} + 2I_1 \delta \otimes \frac{\partial W_2}{\partial \mathbf{C}} + 2W_2 \delta \otimes \frac{\partial I_1}{\partial \mathbf{C}} - 2\mathbf{C} \otimes \frac{\partial W_2}{\partial \mathbf{C}} - 2W_2 \Delta_{\mathbf{C}} \\ -\frac{\partial p}{\partial \mathbf{C}} \otimes \mathbf{C}^{-1} - p \Delta_{\mathbf{C}^{-1}} + 2\mathbf{A}_0 \otimes \frac{\partial W_4}{\partial \mathbf{C}} + 2\mathbf{B}_0 \otimes \frac{\partial W_6}{\partial \mathbf{C}} \end{pmatrix} \quad (11)$$

where $\Delta_{\mathbf{C}} = \frac{\partial \mathbf{C}}{\partial \mathbf{C}}$, $\Delta_{\mathbf{C}^{-1}} = \frac{\partial \mathbf{C}^{-1}}{\partial \mathbf{C}}$, $\mathbf{A}_0 = \mathbf{a}_0 \otimes \mathbf{a}_0$ and $\mathbf{B}_0 = \mathbf{b}_0 \otimes \mathbf{b}_0$.

The material stiffness matrix can be represented by the following relationship for the membrane formulation

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \partial S_X \\ \partial S_Y \\ \partial S_S \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} D_{XX} & D_{XY} & D_{XS} \\ D_{YX} & D_{YY} & D_{YS} \\ D_{SX} & D_{SY} & D_{SS} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \partial E_X \\ \partial E_Y \\ \partial E_S \end{Bmatrix}, \quad (12)$$

where

$$S_X = S_{XX}, S_Y = S_{YY}, S_S = S_{XY} = S_{YX}, \\ E_X = E_{XX} = \frac{1}{2}(C_{XX} - 1), E_Y = E_{YY} = \frac{1}{2}(C_{YY} - 1), E_S = 2E_{XY} = C_{XY}.$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Fitting curves

Figure 2 shows very good fits of the model to experimental data of the bias extension tests. At 170°C and 185°C, the fits are quite perfect. But a slight discrepancy is found at the fitting curve of 155°C when the strain is high. However, this becomes less important as the forming process temperature should be in the vicinity of 170°C and higher. It is also found that WLF function is appropriate for temperature dependence. Figure 3 depicts a great fit of WLF function as temperature dependence of the model. It is observed that in the bias-extension test when the sample is stretched, the fibers rotate under the pure shear until reaching a critical angle [4-5]. As a consequence, the values of M_4 and M_6 , which represent the effect of fibers, are not high compared to other parameters as shown in Table 2. Moreover, M_4 and M_6 have the same values because of the symmetry of the fibers in the bias-extension tests.

Numerical simulation

Figure 4 shows the numerical simulation of the forming of a semi sphere. The FRTPC sheet of 400mm x 400mm x 2mm, having the fibers in the warp and weft directions oriented at $\pm 45^\circ$ compared with the axis of the sheet, is heated to the vicinity of 170°C and then formed by using two molds: male and female. The composite sheet is only clamped at four corners. Four sides of the sheet are free to facilitate shear during forming. Additionally, high slip conditions are imposed at surface contacts between the material and molds to avoid as much as possible the tensile stress in fibers during forming process.

Figure 4. Twintex FRTPC sheet and molds for stamping a semi sphere.

Figure 5. Stamping of a semi sphere with Twintex FRTPC.

Figure 6. View of fiber distribution after forming.

Numerical results of the forming of FRTPC are shown in Figures 5(a-d). Two semi sphere molds close to form the composite. Firstly the molds approach both sides of the composite sheet and then the male mold rises up to deform the composite sheet to get the shape of the female mold. As a consequence, the thickness and fiber directions vary during forming. In these figures, the colors represent the thickness of the composite sheet and the black arrows stand for fibers. Results show that the thickness gradually decreases from the bottom to the top of the semi sphere. This corresponds well to the fact that as high slip condition is imposed between the mold and the composite sheet, the top of the semi sphere should deform the most. The distribution of two families of fibers can be observed more in details on a portion of the composite part as illustrated in Figure 6. A pair of arrows represent two fibers in each element. By connecting them element by element, two families of fibers in the composite part are defined.

These results demonstrate that the proposed model is capable to reasonably describe the deformation of the composite material in stamping process. Numerical simulation can predict the thickness of the composite and fiber change during forming. In future work, new boundary conditions will be implemented to better represent the spring system which is practically used in composite stamping process; more experimental tests will be analyzed for characterizing the Twintex FRTPC materials; and numerical simulations will be validated by comparing with experimental works on stamping of FRTPC.

CONCLUSION

It concludes that in this study:

- The Twintex FRTPC material was modeled with an orthotropic hyperelastic model. The bias extension tests were used to characterize the Twintex FRTPC. Curve fitting results showed that the model fits well experimental data and WLF function is appropriate for temperature dependence.
- The finite element formulation was developed based on the membrane theory to simulate the deformation of the composite sheet in the forming process. Qualitatively good results are found in the prediction of the thickness and fiber change in the composite part.

The slippage between layers, the consolidation and the buckling during stamping of FRTPC sheets are important phenomena that could be observed. These involve multi-body contact problems and flow in deformable porous media, which will be considered in future work.

NOMENCLATURE

W	Strain energy function
λ	Stretch ratio
σ	Cauchy stress tensor
S	2 nd Piola-Kirchhoff stress tensor
F	Deformation gradient tensor
x	Coordinates in the deformed configuration
X	Coordinates in the initial configuration
C	Right Cauchy-Green deformation tensor
E	Green-Lagrange deformation tensor
V	Element volume
A	Element surface

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We would like to gratefully thank the Polymers Composites Group of IMI, NRC for experimental works, particularly Dr. Johanne Denault and Dr. Martin Bureau.

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